

The Role and Function of English Language in ESP Classes

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Abstract: English is taught to students whose first language is not English but who require it for a specific task, activity, or goal through ESP. The acronym ESP stands for "English for Specific Purposes," also known as "English for Special Purposes." Although it is widely accepted that teaching ESP courses should emphasize language skills such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking, this often depends on the needs and interests of the students. The course design for English for Specific Purposes, the role of the teacher and student in ESP, and difficulties related to the environment, the student, and other factors in ESP teaching are all covered in this article.

Keywords: ESP, the role of students and teacher, course design, responsibility, environment, objectives.

The term "specific" in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) refers to the specific purpose of learning English (Hans and Hans, 2015). The English for Specific Purposes (ESP) approach improves the relevance of what the students/learners are learning, then enables them to use English that they have known before. English for Specific Purposes (ESP) assesses the students/learners' needs and it integrates motivation, subject matter, and content for the teaching of relevant skills. Almost every subject has its own "term" used in the course, such as business, medicine, and various scientific and technical fields. These terms can be both much more complicated and complex. Because English is widespread, it is becoming more and more important to learn English for Specific Purposes (ESP). The most important learner's purpose for learning English is to communicate a set of professional skills and to perform specific job-related functions. English for Specific Purposes (ESP), therefore, built on an assessment of purposes and needs and the functions for which English is required.

English for specific purposes (ESP) refers to the teaching and learning of English as a second or foreign language where the goal of the learners is to use English in a particular domain (Fitria, 2019). Hans and Hans (2015) state that English for Specific Purposes (ESP) more concentrates on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures. An important point in ESP that English is not taught as a subject separated from the students' real world, but it is integrated into a subject matter area important to the learners. English for Specific Purposes (ESP), needs analysis that determines which language skills are most needed by the students/learners, and the syllabus is designed appropriately for the students/learners. English for Specific Purposes (ESP) program can be used to emphasize the development of English skills in students/learners who are preparing for graduate work in business administration, or it promotes the development of spoken skills in students who are studying English in order to become tourist guides, etc. Based on the explanation above, it is perceived that ESP is goal-oriented and focused on English teaching and learning, designed for the specific learners according to learners' academic and needs.

The fact is English for Specific Purposes (ESP) combines subject matter and English language teaching like a combination is highly motivating because the students/learners can apply what they have learned in their English classes to their field of studies such as in accounting, business,

management, economics, computer science, agriculture, politic or tourism. Being able to use the vocabularies and structures that they have to learn in a meaningful context, it reinforces what is taught and increases their motivation in learning English. The students' abilities in their subject-matter fields, improve their skill to acquire or master English. Subject-matter knowledge gives the students/learners the context they need to understand English in the classroom. In English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classes, the students/learners are shown how the subject-matter content is expressed well in English. The teachers can make the most of the students' knowledge of the subject matter so that it helps them can learn English faster. For that reason, this article will bring information about course design of English for Specific Purposes, the role of the teacher and student in ESP and challenges associated with the environment, the student, and other factors in ESP teaching.

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) the emphasis is on “Specific English” that belongs to any particular discipline, occupation or activity (Javid, 2015). English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has become a fruitful field over the last three decades. (Ramirez, 2015). As a learner-centered approach, its main purpose has been that of fulfilling the specific needs of target learners to satisfy their professional or vocational demands.

Hutchinson and Waters (1987) state that in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) context, the outcomes of the historical occurrences resulted from a number of people across the globe who wanted to learn the English language due to the key language in the fields of science, technology, and commerce. The emergence of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) teaching movement is caused by the English language needs of the learners for specific purposes in relation to their professions or job description. Howatt (1984) states that since the emergent years in the 1960s, ESP has become a vital and innovative activity within the Teaching of English as a Foreign or Second Language movement (TEFL/TESL). Hutchinson and Waters (1987) define that ESP is an approach to language learning and it is based on learners' needs. It shows that ESP does not involve a particular kind of language, teaching material or methodology”, but they suggest that the foundation of ESP involves the learners, the language required and the learning contexts which are based on the primacy of need in English for Specific Purposes (ESP).

Do and Cai (2010) state that ESP is English courses based on survey results and needs analysis in order to determine the specific activities that students/learners have to do as well as the final goal they want to achieve. Therefore, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is an English course in which the textbooks and materials are adjusted to learners' desires and purposes. Robinson's (1991: 3) definition of ESP is based on two criteria they are: 1) ESP is normally 'goal-directed', and 2) ESP courses are developed from a needs analysis which aim to specify what exactly it is that the students have to go through the medium of English, and a number of characteristics which explain that ESP courses are generally constrained by a limited time period in which their objectives/goals have to be achieved and are taught to adults in homogenous and various classes in terms of the work or specialist studies that the students/learners are involved in. Based on the definitions above, it can be concluded that English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is learning English for a specific purpose to get specific goals. Needs assessment or need analysis in ESP reaching ESP should not be considered as a different kind of teaching the language, but it is as an approach as it is also based on the common belief of teaching language for communicative purposes.

EAP (English for Academic Purposes) refers to any English teaching that relates to academic study needs (Dudley-Evans & St. John, 1998; Robinson, 1991; Hutchinson & Waters, 1987: 2). ESP students are usually adults who already have some acquaintance with English and are learning the language in order to communicate a set of professional skills and to perform particular job-related functions. An ESP program is therefore built on an assessment of purposes and needs and the functions for which English is required.

Language curriculum development frequently begins with determining how syllabus design can address the specific needs and desires of learners. The study addressed the need for current

descriptions of students' language needs as well as the provision of English programs.

ESP were traditionally designed for intermediate or advanced adult learners. Many students can now begin learning academic or vocational English at a younger age and at a lower level of proficiency. In this study, a teacher must create materials based on the needs of students studying English for Academic Purposes, specifically students. Furthermore, the teacher should demonstrate it in the classroom. As the audience, the learners were asked to fill out questionnaires based on their needs in the ESP class.

ESP concentrates more on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures. It covers subjects varying from accounting or computer science to tourism and business management. The ESP focal point is that English is not taught as a subject separated from the students' real world (or wishes); instead, it is integrated into a subject matter area important to the learners.

However, ESL and ESP diverge not only in the nature of the learner, but also in the aim of instruction. In fact, as a general rule, while in ESL all four language skills; listening, reading, speaking, and writing, are stressed equally, in ESP it is a needs analysis that determines which language skills are most needed by the students, and the syllabus is designed accordingly. An ESP program, might, for example, emphasize the development of reading skills in students who are preparing for graduate work in business administration; or it might promote the development of spoken skills in students who are studying English in order to become tourist guides.

As a matter of fact, ESP combines subject matter and English language teaching. Such a combination is highly motivating because students are able to apply what they learn in their English classes to their main field of study, whether it be accounting, business management, economics, computer science or tourism. Being able to use the vocabulary and structures that they learn in a meaningful context reinforces what is taught and increases their motivation.

The students' abilities in their subject-matter fields, in turn, improve their ability to acquire English. Subject-matter knowledge gives them the context they need to understand the English of the classroom. In the ESP class, students are shown how the subject-matter content is expressed in English. The teacher can make the most of the students' knowledge of the subject matter, thus helping them learn English faster.

The term "specific" in ESP refers to the specific purpose for learning English. Students approach the study of English through a field that is already known and relevant to them. This means that they are able to use what they learn in the ESP classroom right away in their work and studies. The ESP approach enhances the relevance of what the students are learning and enables them to use the English they know to learn even more English, since their interest in their field will motivate them to interact with speakers and texts.

ESP assesses needs and integrates motivation, subject matter and content for the teaching of relevant skills.

The responsibility of the teacher

A teacher that already has experience in teaching English as a Second Language (ESL), can exploit her background in language teaching. She should recognize the ways in which her teaching skills can be adapted for the teaching of English for Specific Purposes. Moreover, she will need to look for content specialists for help in designing appropriate lessons in the subject matter field she is teaching.

As an ESP teacher, you must play many roles. You may be asked to organize courses, to set learning objectives, to establish a positive learning environment in the classroom, and to evaluate student s progress.

Organizing Courses

You have to set learning goals and then transform them into an instructional program with the

timing of activities. One of your main tasks will be selecting, designing and organizing course materials, supporting the students in their efforts, and providing them with feedback on their progress.

Setting Goals and Objectives

You arrange the conditions for learning in the classroom and set long-term goals and short-term objectives for students achievement. Your knowledge of students' potential is central in designing a syllabus with realistic goals that takes into account the students' concern in the learning situation.

Creating a Learning Environment

Your skills for communication and mediation create the classroom atmosphere. Students acquire language when they have opportunities to use the language in interaction with other speakers. Being their teacher, you may be the only English speaking person available to students, and although your time with any of them is limited, you can structure effective communication skills in the classroom. In order to do so, in your interactions with students try to listen carefully to what they are saying and give your understanding or misunderstanding back at them through your replies.

Good language learners are also great risk-takers , since they must make many errors in order to succeed: however, in ESP classes, they are handicapped because they are unable to use their native language competence to present themselves as well-informed adults. That's why the teacher should create an atmosphere in the language classroom which supports the students. Learners must be self-confident in order to communicate, and you have the responsibility to help build the learner's confidence.

Evaluating Students

The teacher is a resource that helps students identify their language learning problems and find solutions to them, find out the skills they need to focus on, and take responsibility for making choices which determine what and how to learn. You will serve as a source of information to the students about how they are progressing in their language learning.

The responsibility of the student

What is the role of the learner and what is the task he/she faces? The learners come to the ESP class with a specific interest for learning, subject matter knowledge, and well-built adult learning strategies. They are in charge of developing English language skills to reflect their native-language knowledge and skills.

Interest for Learning

People learn languages when they have opportunities to understand and work with language in a context that they comprehend and find interesting. In this view, ESP is a powerful means for such opportunities. Students will acquire English as they work with materials which they find interesting and relevant and which they can use in their professional work or further studies. The more learners pay attention to the meaning of the language they hear or read, the more they are successful; the more they have to focus on the linguistic input or isolated language structures, the less they are motivated to attend their classes.

The ESP student is particularly well disposed to focus on meaning in the subject-matter field. In ESP, English should be presented not as a subject to be learned in isolation from real use, nor as a mechanical skill or habit to be developed. On the contrary, English should be presented in authentic contexts to make the learners acquainted with the particular ways in which the language is used in functions that they will need to perform in their fields of specialty or jobs.

Subject-Content Knowledge

Learners in the ESP classes are generally aware of the purposes for which they will need to use English. Having already oriented their education toward a specific field, they see their English training as complementing this orientation. Knowledge of the subject area enables the students to identify a real context for the vocabulary and structures of the ESP classroom. In such way, the learners can take advantage of what they already know about the subject matter to learn English.

Learning Strategies

Adults must work harder than children in order to learn a new language, but the learning skills they bring to the task permit them to learn faster and more efficiently. The skills they have already developed in using their native languages will make learning English easier. Although you will be working with students whose English will probably be quite limited, the language learning abilities of the adult in the ESP classroom are potentially immense. Educated adults are continually learning new language behavior in their native languages, since language learning continues naturally throughout our lives. They are constantly expanding vocabulary, becoming more fluent in their fields, and adjusting their linguistic behaviour to new situations or new roles. ESP students can exploit these innate competencies in learning English.

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